

1. Title:

Design and Development of an Intercom Security System to Prevent Door Lock Solenoid Activation via the Panel

2. Abstract:

In many audios and video intercom systems (Intercom), removing the panel from its mounting box and connecting two points of the panel circuit with a conductive tool allows the door lock solenoid to be activated, enabling easy unauthorized access to the premises. This situation compromises residential security and facilitates potential misuse by intruders. The present study focuses on the design and development of a security and anti-theft system for intercoms, where the 12V AC power supply to the door lock passes through this system before reaching the panel. If the panel is removed from its box, a microswitch immediately cuts off the power to the panel in less than one-hundredth of a second and activates an alarm. This approach effectively prevents unauthorized access to the door lock circuit while ensuring easy installation and cost-effective operation.

3. Keywords:

Security system, Audio and video intercom, Electric door lock, Anti-theft, Microswitch, 12V AC power, Residential protection, Alarm

4. Introduction:

With the increasing use of audio and video door entry systems in residential, corporate, and institutional settings, the security and privacy of occupants have gained significant importance. Many intercoms available on the market, both domestic and foreign, allow the door lock to be activated by direct access to the panel circuit. This security vulnerability enables unauthorized individuals to misuse the system and gain entry without the consent of the residents. The present invention, titled "iPhone Security System to Prevent Door Lock Coil Activation via Panel," is designed to be installed near the intercom's power supply. It interrupts the panel's power in case the panel is removed from its housing, preventing unauthorized activation of the door lock. The system operates in less than one hundredth of a second while simultaneously triggering an alarm, and power is only restored to the panel through manual system reset by the residents. Consequently, the security of homes is significantly enhanced.

5. Prior Art Review:

Research indicates that in Iran, only one anti-theft intercom has been officially registered (Application No. 139250140003003290; Patent No. 80738). This anti-theft intercom solely provides the capability of securing the panel without screws, and its door lock mechanism functions like other intercoms available in the country.

The main issue with existing intercoms is the ability to activate the door lock via direct access to the panel circuit. By simply connecting two points of the circuit with a conductive wire, the door lock coil can be triggered, allowing unauthorized entry. Even intercoms equipped with a basic alarm system can be bypassed through simple mechanical force or by disconnecting a specific wire, enabling the door lock to operate without triggering any alert.

Therefore, none of the existing models can prevent door lock activation when the panel is removed, and prior systems lack the rapid power cut-off and simultaneous alarm functionality. This security gap highlights the need for a new system design that protects the door lock operation and minimizes unauthorized entry.

It is noteworthy that the invention discussed in this article has been officially registered (Patent No. 102060; Title: Design and Construction of an iPhone Security System to Prevent Door Lock Coil Activation via Panel; Inventor: Navid Mehrjoo). This invention demonstrates innovation in the security and anti-theft performance of intercoms, with practical advantages over existing systems, including higher safety and ease of installation. Hence, this article presents a scientific description of the design, construction, and application of this system.

6. Objectives and Advantages:

The primary objective of this invention is to enhance home security and prevent unauthorized access to the intercom door lock. By using the security and anti-theft system, the power supply to the intercom panel first passes through this system. If the panel is removed from its holder, the input power to the panel is cut off in less than one-hundredth of a second, blocking access to activate the door lock. This mechanism ensures that even with physical access to the panel, the door lock coil cannot be triggered without the presence of the residents.

6.1: The main advantages of the invention include:

6.1.1: Enhanced Security: Prevents unauthorized activation of the door lock and reduces the risk of theft and intrusion into homes .

6.1.2: Cost-Effective: The system can be easily installed on all existing intercoms without requiring redesign or modifications to the intercom or its production line .

6.1.3: Easy Installation: By connecting two AC wires from the power supply to the panel and buzzer, the system can be simply installed and operated .

6.1.4: Durability and Easy Maintenance: The system's low current (approximately 800 mA) ensures long operational life and easy maintenance, and its components are readily available in the market .

6.1.5: Performance Monitoring and Assurance: The use of a voltmeter and DC-to-DC voltage reduction module ensures system functionality, and economical models without indicators can also be produced .

6.1.6: Complete Coil Protection: The door lock coil is powered through the security system, preventing reactivation of the coil after the panel power is cut.

7. Implementation and Installation Method:

The most effective way to implement this system is to install it near the intercom power supply. If the intercom wiring has already been completed, installing the system adjacent to the power supply facilitates easy connection and wiring. In older homes where the intercom power supply may be located in the garage wall, near the unit entrance, or in the stairwell, and typically branches from the main electrical panel, the security system can be installed in the electrical panel box, with the necessary wiring extended from there to the intercom panel.

7.1: The installation procedure includes the following steps:

7.1.1 Connecting two AC wires (12V) from the power supply to the security system.

7.1.2 Extending two power wires from the security system to the intercom panel.

7.1.3 Connecting two DC wires from the security system to the buzzer installed in the microswitch circuit.

7.1.4: Connecting three additional wires from the system to the microswitch to control the disconnection and reconnection of the panel's input power.

The positions of all wires are clearly marked in the circuit, and with numbered labeling, even individuals without specialized knowledge can install and operate the system. This method ensures a fast, safe, and reliable installation of the security system.

8. Design and Construction of the Intercom Security System

The intercom security and anti-theft system was designed and constructed based on a detailed technical schematic that defines all connections, components, and circuit operations. The design ensures rapid disconnection of panel power and simultaneous alarm activation in the event of unauthorized panel removal. The system includes the following sections:

8.1: AC Power Supply and Connection to the Intercom Panel

The 12V AC power first enters the security system before being routed to the intercom panel. This ensures that any attempt to remove the panel from its housing immediately interrupts the panel's input power, preventing activation of the door lock solenoid.

8.2: Microswitch and Alarm Circuit

A microswitch is installed inside the panel box. When the panel is removed, the microswitch activates in less than 0.01 seconds, cutting off the panel power and simultaneously triggering a 12V DC buzzer alarm. Additional wiring allows control over the on/off operation, ensuring that power to the panel can only be restored manually from inside the building.

8.3: Electric Lock Solenoid Power Protection

The door lock solenoid is powered through the security system circuit. This design prevents reactivation of the solenoid even if an external battery or other power source is applied after panel disconnection, guaranteeing complete protection.

8.4: Components and Tools Used

The system utilizes widely available components, including:

- One-sided fiberglass PCB (9 × 12 cm)
- Microswitch with COM, NO, NC terminals
- Double-pole two-way switch with neutral and dual outputs
- Relay modules (12V DC, JQC-3F-1C-12VDC)
- DC-to-DC voltage reduction module (LM2596)
- AC and DC panel voltmeters
- Diodes, resistors, capacitors, LEDs, and buzzers as required

The system's low current consumption (~800 mA) ensures long-term durability and easy maintenance.

8.5: Assembly and Installation of Components

All components are mounted in a suitable plastic or metal enclosure. Wiring is performed according to the technical schematic with numbered positions for all wires, enabling straightforward and error-free installation even by non-specialists.

8.6: Schematic Diagram and Operational Flow

The technical schematic and operational flow diagram illustrate:

- Power flow from the AC source to the intercom panel
- Activation of the microswitch and buzzer alarm
- Routing of solenoid power through the security circuit
- Manual reset mechanism via the two-way switch

Figures 1 and 2 show the main circuit schematic and the solenoid wiring diagram, providing a clear reference for reproducibility and scientific examination.

9. Industrial Application:

The security and anti-theft system for disabling the intercom door lock has broad applications across various industries and environments. This system is suitable for all audio and video intercoms and electric door locks used in residential homes, offices, factories, and both governmental and non-governmental organizations.

9.1: The main industrial applications of this invention include:

9.1.1: Enhancing the security of residents in homes and personnel in office and industrial environments.

9.1.2: Preventing unauthorized access to intercom systems and protecting property and information.

9.1.3: Enabling easy installation in any location where an intercom is installed, without requiring changes to the design or model of the intercom.

9.1.4: Reducing the risk of theft and intrusion by malicious individuals who may access the intercom panel circuitry.

Due to its simple design, high efficiency, and compatibility with various intercom models, this system can be deployed industrially and commercially in any environment where entry security is a priority.

10. Results and Advantages:

The security and anti-theft system for disabling the intercom door lock demonstrates

10.1: significant results, which are detailed below:

10.1.1: Enhanced home and occupant security :

The system instantly cuts the intercom panel's power supply if it is removed from its housing, preventing unauthorized activation of the door lock solenoid. The response time of the system is less than 0.01 seconds, completely blocking intruders' access to the panel circuit and the ability to trigger the lock.

10.1.2: No modification required for existing intercoms :

The system is designed for installation on all existing audio and video intercoms without redesigning the panel or altering the production line. This feature allows easy implementation in existing homes and buildings.

10.1.3: Simple installation by non-specialists :

Installation is straightforward using the labeled wires and catalog instructions. By connecting two AC wires to the power source and a few wires to the microswitch, the system becomes operational without requiring specialized electronics knowledge.

10.1.4: High durability and easy maintenance :

The low output current of the system (approximately 800 mA) ensures long-lasting components. Troubleshooting and repair can be performed with simple tools such as a multimeter, and the components are readily available in the market.

10.1.5: Voltage indicators and cost reduction options :

Two panel voltmeters and a DC-to-DC step-down module ensure accurate system performance. Models without voltage indicators can also be produced, reducing the total cost by half and making the technology more accessible to the general public.

10.1.6: Isolation of the door lock solenoid power :

The solenoid is powered through the security system circuit and is designed so that even if the panel power is cut, reactivation of the solenoid by external sources or batteries is impossible. This feature fully secures the operational integrity of the door lock.

11. Conclusion:

Based on the conducted analyses and tests, the security and anti-theft system for disabling intercom door locks provides an effective, cost-efficient, and practical solution for enhancing the security of homes and buildings. With easy installation, high durability, simple maintenance, and no need to modify existing intercoms, this system addresses the security weaknesses of current intercom panels on the market. By preventing direct access

to the door lock circuit, it safeguards against theft, intrusion, and harassment, ensuring the safety of occupants. Its industrial application is broad and practical, suitable for homes, offices, factories, and both governmental and non-governmental institutions utilizing audio and video intercom systems.

12. Figures:

Figures 1: Main circuit schematic

Figures 2: Lock opener schematic